

Impact of Artificial Pollen Diet on Colony Productivity in Stingless Bee, *Tetragonula iridipennis* (Smith) (Apidae: Hymenoptera) During Dearth Period

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Abstract: ,ksa

The present investigation evaluated the impacts of various artificial diets of pollen substitute on stingless bee (*Tetragonula iridipennis*) colony productivity and foraging behaviour during dearth season from June to October 2023. The treatments of pollen substitutes were prepared using combinations of parched soybean and Bengal gram powders, milk powder, sugar and honey. Each colony was supplemented with 3.0 g of the diet biweekly. Observations were made on the diet consumption, colony productivity and foraging behaviour. The diet consumption was highest in T₅ (2.66±0.10 g) in the treatment of Bengal gram flour added with pollen grain, skimmed milk powder, sugar, glucose and honey and the lowest consumption in T₁ (0.81±0.34 g) of soybean flour base treatment. Colony productivity was also highest in T₅ with significant increases in brood cells (82.41±16.79/in³), Pollen pots (6.88±1.57/in³) and honey pots (12.04±2.56/in³). Correspondingly in T₅ the foraging behaviour also highest from 1300 to 1400 h, with maximum outgoing bees (7.71 bees/5min h), pollen foragers (3.43) and nectar foragers (4.86). Resin foragers peaked between 1600 and 1700 h (2.14 bees/5min/h). The findings suggest that the diet constituting 12.5% each Bengal gram flour and pollen grain combination with other ingredients significantly enhances colony productivity and influences foraging behaviour, providing a valuable strategy for beekeepers to mitigate the effects of dearth periods and climatic changes on stingless bee colonies.

Keywords: *Tetragonula iridipennis*, Pollen supplement, Colony development, Foraging, Dearth season.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The stingless bees are highly eusocial, corbiculate with perennial colonies, polylectic, docile for handling and conservation, forager recruitment behaviour, ability to store more resources in hive unlike honeybees [1]. The nesting place of stingless bees are in stone walls, hollows of tree trunks, mud walls, termitarium and cracks and crevices with suitable insulation [2]. Among the insect pollinators, stingless bees are reported to be efficient pollinators of many crops like tomato, cucumber, brinjal, strawberry and sweet pepper and could be viably utilized for pollination of crops grown under protected cultivations [3, 4]. Eusocial bees have further multifaceted requirements for their huge population, prolonged activity and incapability to develop daughter colonies deprived of worker bees. Colonies adopt more strategies to save energy and food when the colony individuals decrease, shortage of food for broods and the external activities of workers get reduced to prolong their life spans. In their evolutionary process, the key solution to overcome the dearth period is storage of food sources which allows them to be active perennially [5, 6, 7]. The provision of artificial diet to insects is primarily developed to investigate the basic nutritional needs for effective growth and development under laboratory conditions especially for insect mass culturing [8]. Most of the bees feed on pollen and nectar rather than *Trigona hypogea*, which feeds on decomposing cadavers for nutrients. The pollen is the major source of protein, vitamins, lipids and mineral salts [9] whereas nectar provides carbohydrates [10]. The pollen quality can affect the bee ovarian activation, longevity and physiological mechanisms. During dearth period in lack of pollen, the colony health is directly affected by reduced larval food production, fecundity, nutrient intake of egg laying queens and number of offsprings [11, 12]. The endurance of an arthropod life is highly dependent on dietary intake linked with its health, nutritional value, physical fitness and ambient conditions like temperature and humidity [13]. Stingless bees are possessed with chewing and lapping type of mouth parts which enable them to forage nectar and pollen as their natural diet from plants within their flight range. The activities like foraging and colony defense resulted in high mortality. Bee's longevity and survival rate get declined when their physical and metabolic activity increases [14, 15]. Modern laboratories that associated with the entomological research regularly practice the provision of artificial diet to maintain the insect colonies. In adult stage, nutrients play significant role in their strength, increasing female lifespan and their reproductive performance [16, 17].

Stingless bees have evolved more than 70 million years for developing the strategies such as to preserve the stored food without the spoilage and loss of nutritional quality [18]. The pollen collection and processing by stingless bees is undeniably very complex and therefore knowledge about their general composition of protein, lipids and carbohydrates are limited. The hypopharyngeal gland development in *Scaptotrigona depilis* workers is significant when fed with the fermented mixture of yeast, pollen and sucrose solution (50%) than the natural diet [19, 20]. Soybean is one of the commonly used ingredients for artificial diet due to their lower cost and wide availability in market [21]. By providing the artificial protein diet to stingless bees, the nutritional value can be estimated through their colony level such as effect on longevity of workers, brood cell, pollen and honey pots production and larval development [22]. The main aim of the present study was to devise an artificial diet as a substitute for pollen during the period of pollen shortage to promote and sustain the colony productivity.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted at the insectary premises of Agricultural College and Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India (9° 58' 41" N; 78° 12' 10" E) during the dearth season from June to October 2023. The pollen substitutes were prepared by using different combination of powders from parched soybean, Bengal gram along with milk powder, sugar and honey (Table 1). Each stingless bee colonies was provided with 3.0 g of pollen substitute with different treatments at fortnight interval. The observations on colony productivity were recorded at fortnight interval by measuring the density of brood, pollen and honey pots per cubic inch [23]. The diet consumption by the colony individuals was

recorded by quantifying the diet left over and consumed diet. With slight modifications the annotations on foraging behaviour of stingless bees were recorded by providing the significant pollen substitute at the month end of dearth season. Four types of bee foragers and their activities were observed in terms of number of worker bees going out and coming in with their rewards such as pollen, nectar and resin for five minutes per hour during random hours from 0700 to 1700 h in a day at the hive entrance. The key interpretation attributes were recorded at every four days interval during a month in dearth season [24, 25]. The data analysis was performed using R Studio with the “stats” package for one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s hoc test to assess the significance in colony productivity and “agricolae” package for the Duncan’s Median Range Test (DMRT) to find the peak foraging time of worker bees [26].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The stingless bee colonies were provided with protein food supplement for consumption throughout the dearth season instead of natural pollen foraging. Among the different treatments, the quantity of the diet consumed by the stingless bees is high (2.66 ± 0.19 g) in T_5 (Bengal Gram Flour 12.5% + Pollen Grain 12.5% + Skimmed Milk Powder 25% + Sugar 6% + Glucose 12% + Honey 32%) followed by T_3 (2.27 ± 0.35 g) and the least consumption (0.81 ± 0.34 g) was recorded in T_1 (Soybean Flour - Soy Flour 25% + Skimmed Milk Powder 25% + Sugar 6% + Glucose 12% + Honey 32%) and vice versa for the quantity of the diet left over by the stingless bee from different treatments. It is fairly analogous with the findings of Vollet-Neto *et al.* [27] who conveyed that bees desire fermented pollen with flour mixtures instead of freshly prepared diet. The colony productivity of stingless bees was determined by observing the development of brood pots, pollen pots and honey pots volume in their colony (Table 2). The colony supplemented with the treatment (T_5 – Bengal gram + Pollen grain) recorded to have high volume of brood pots ($82.41 \pm 16.79/\text{in}^3$), pollen pots ($6.88 \pm 1.57/\text{in}^3$) and honey pots ($12.04 \pm 2.56/\text{in}^3$) followed by T_3 (Pollen grain), which resulted brood ($75.29 \pm 14.36/\text{in}^3$), pollen ($6.5 \pm 1.92/\text{in}^3$) and honey pots ($11.00 \pm 2.86/\text{in}^3$) volume. The smallest amount of brood ($54.63 \pm 8.49/\text{in}^3$), pollen ($4.58 \pm 1.64/\text{in}^3$) and honey pots ($8.16 \pm 2.23/\text{in}^3$) were noticed from the colony supplemented with the treatment (T_1 – Soybean flour). This finding was fairly consistent with Queiroz *et al.* [21] who reported that the adult workers bees of *Melipona flavolineata* and *Scaptotrigona aff. postica* showed high survival rate when fed with pollen than soy treatment. This similarity depicts that, the soybean flour was not preferred by the diversified stingless bee groups including *T. iridipennis*. Also, harmonized with the findings of Paray *et al.* [28] who specified that the proteinaceous supplements showed substantial enrichment in all parameters of colony productivity like colony strength and weight, percent consumption of food and honey production even in dearth period. At the end of dearth season, among the treatments, the significant artificial pollen diet was fed to stingless bee colony to determine the foraging behaviour of bees with respect to artificial diet. The maximum number of outgoing bees (7.71 bees/5min/h), pollen foragers (3.43) and nectar foragers (4.86) were recorded between 1300 to 1400 h with mean of seven days. The highest resin foragers (2.14 bees/5min/h) were observed between 1600 and 1700 h. All the four types of bee foragers (outgoing, pollen, nectar and resin foragers) showed least activity (1.71, 0.71, 0.86 and 0.43 bees/5min/h) from 0700 to 0800 h respectively (Table 3). This result is unreliable with the finding of Saai Vignesh *et al.* [25] who stated that the highest pollen and nectar foragers were observed between 1100 and 1200 h where the colony had been placed in coriander field for pollination. Also, consistent with the finding of Roopa *et al.* [29] who observed the peak pollen and nectar foragers between 1300 and 1400 h during monsoon season. The rate of bees on foraging got reduced due to the supplementary food inside the colony and increased due to nature of crop where the colony hived, and showed the inconsistencies.

IV. CONCLUSION

In the present investigation, the impact of artificial diet upon feeding by stingless bees increased the colony productivity significantly during dearth period. The significant pollen substitute suitable for the stingless bee was found to be the mixture of Bengal gram flour + Pollen grain under the composition of Bengal Gram Flour 12.5% + Pollen Grain 12.5% + Skimmed Milk Powder 25% + Sugar 6% + Glucose 12% + Honey 32% which resulted in increased colony productivity. Artificial diet had also influenced the bee foraging behaviour. The outcome of this study is useful mitigate the dearth period and climatic changes faced by the stingless bee and beekeepers.

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DECLARATIONS

We confirm that the results are presented clearly, honestly and without fabrication, falsification or inappropriate data manipulation. Additionally, no data, text or theories by others are presented.

1. **Ethics approval and consent to participate** - Not applicable
2. **Consent for publication** – All authors declare that there are no issues relating to journal policies.
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TABLE I
COMPOSITION OF POLLEN SUBSTITUTES

Treatments	Pollen substitute	Composition of diet
T ₁	Soybean flour	Soy Flour 25% + Skimmed Milk Powder 25% + Sugar 6% + Glucose 12% + Honey 32%
T ₂	Bengal gram flour	Bengal Gram Flour 25% + Skimmed Milk Powder 25% + Sugar 6% + Glucose 12% + Honey 32%
T ₃	Pollen grain	Pollen Grain 25% + Skimmed Milk Powder 25% + Sugar 6% + Glucose 12% + Honey 32%
T ₄	Soybean flour + Pollen grain	Soy Flour 12.5% + Pollen Grain 12.5% + Skimmed Milk Powder 25% + Sugar 6% + Glucose 12% + Honey 32%
T ₅	Bengal gram flour + Pollen grain	Bengal Gram Flour 12.5% + Pollen Grain 12.5% + Skimmed Milk Powder 25% + Sugar 6% + Glucose 12% + Honey 32%
T ₆	Fermented Pollen grain	Pollen Grain 25% + Skimmed Milk Powder 25% + Sugar 6% + Glucose 12% + Honey 32% + Lactic Acid Bacteria inoculum 50 ml
T ₇	Control	-

TABLE II
STINGLESS BEE COLONY PRODUCTIVITY ON CONSUMPTION OF ARTIFICIAL POLLEN DIET

Treatments	Quantity (g/hive)	Consumption of Diet (g)		Brood Cells/cu.in	Pollen Pots/cu.in	Honey Pots/cu.in
		*QLD	*CD			
T1	3	2.18±0.19 (1.64) ^a	0.81±0.34 (1.13) ^d	54.63±8.49 (7.37) ^f	4.58±1.64 (2.11) ^d	8.16±2.23 (8.17) ^f
T2	3	1.39±0.22 (1.37) ^b	1.64±0.29 (1.46) ^c	62.54±10.38 (7.86) ^d	5.58±2.83 (2.29) ^c	10.04±2.15 (10.04) ^c
T3	3	0.68±0.17 (1.08) ^d	2.27±0.35 (1.66) ^b	75.29±14.36 (8.64) ^b	6.5±1.92 (2.52) ^{ab}	11.00±2.86 (10.99) ^b
T4	3	1.56±0.17 (1.43) ^b	1.39±0.29 (1.37) ^c	56.13±6.22 (7.48) ^{ef}	4.91±1.93 (2.18) ^{cd}	8.92±2.34 (8.92) ^e
T5	3	0.38±0.16 (0.94) ^e	2.66±0.19 (1.78) ^a	82.41±16.79 (9.04) ^a	6.88±1.57 (2.61) ^a	12.04±2.56 (12.04) ^a
T6	3	0.98±0.29 (1.21) ^c	1.98±0.22 (1.57) ^b	67.58±13.54 (8.19) ^c	6.13±1.59 (2.46) ^b	10.63±2.39 (10.62) ^b
T7 (Control)	0	0	0	59.17±9.02 (7.67) ^{de}	5.38±2.00 (2.28) ^c	9.45±1.89 (9.46) ^d

*Each value is a mean of eight fortnight intervals. Figures in parenthesis are square root transformed values; Means followed by same alphabet(s) are on par by DMRT (p=0.05). QLD – Quantity Left-over Diet; CD - Consumed Diet.

TABLE III
FORAGING ACTIVITY OF STINGLESS BEES UPON CONSUMING THE SIGNIFICANT POLLEN SUBSTITUTE (BENGAL GRAM FLOUR + POLLEN GRAIN)

Time of hours	*Number of bees/5min/h			
	Outgoing foragers	Pollen foragers	Nectar foragers	Resin foragers
0700 – 0800	1.71 (1.44) ^d	0.71 (1.05) ^c	0.86 (1.13) ^c	0.43 (0.93) ^b
1000 – 1100	5.43 (2.43) ^b	1.71 (1.47) ^b	3.43 (1.96) ^{bc}	1.43 (1.35) ^{ab}
1300 – 1400	7.71 (2.85) ^a	3.43 (1.95) ^a	4.86 (2.29) ^a	1.14 (1.23) ^{ab}
1600 – 1700	3.00 (1.86) ^c	2.71 (1.77) ^{ab}	4.14 (2.08) ^b	2.14 (1.60) ^a

*No. of bees going out and coming in with rewards for five minutes in a random hour. Each value is a mean of seven observations. Figures in parenthesis are square root transformed values; Means followed by same alphabet(s) are on par by DMRT (p=0.05)